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ON FIRST INTEGRALS OF A SIXTH-ORDER ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATION

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Abstract. In the paper, constructive methods for finding some first integrals of a sixth-order ordinary differential equation with a potential operator are suggested. We use some methods based on application of transformation of variables to establish invariance of the given sixth-order ordinary differential equation with the potential operator and the corresponding Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action. Some first integrals of the considered equation are also found.

Keywords: *Sixth-order ordinary differential equation, potential operator, Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action, symmetry, divergence invariance, first integral*

INTRODUCTION

Variational principles play an important role in the mechanics of both finite-dimensional and infinite-dimensional systems. The use of some methods of mechanics is associated with the existence of direct or indirect variational formulations of the equations of motion, which can be used, for example, to find the first integrals of the considered equations. Note that, in particular, the works [1–10] are devoted to construction of variational formulations of various types of equations and their systems.

Studying the existence and determining the structure of first integrals of different types of equations and their systems are important and urgent problems. The first integrals of differential equations have various applications: they are used to prove the existence and uniqueness of solutions [11–13], to study the stability of motion of some infinite-dimensional systems [14], etc. Problems of finding the first integrals can be related to the symmetry properties of functionals and the corresponding Euler-Lagrange equations. For Euler functionals, the connection between symmetries and conservation laws was established in [15]. A wide interest in finding conservation laws with the use of symmetries is associated with the fundamental monographs of L.V. Ovsyannikov [16] and N.Kh. Ibragimov [17].

Symmetries are also widely used in the qualitative analysis of the motion of finite-dimensional systems [18]. Note that the works [1, 19–23] are devoted to relationships of the symmetries of equations and functionals with the first integrals of the equations of motion of infinite-dimensional systems. The present work is their continuation.

Assume that U, V are real linear normed spaces. The following definition and theorem will be needed for the sequel.

Definition 1. [1] An operator $N : D(N) \subset U \rightarrow V$ is called potential on the set $D(N)$ relative to a bilinear form $\Phi(\cdot, \cdot) : V \times V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ if there exists a Gâteaux differentiable functional $F_N : D(F_N) = D(N) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\delta F_N[u, h] = \Phi(N(u), h) \quad \forall u \in D(N), \forall h \in D(N'_u). \quad (1)$$

In this case, it is said that the corresponding equation $N(u) = 0$ admits a direct variational formulation.

Theorem 1. [1] Consider a Gâteaux differentiable operator $N : D(N) \subset U \rightarrow V$ and a bilinear form $\Phi(\cdot, \cdot) : V \times V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that for any fixed elements $u \in D(N)$, $g, h \in D(N'_u)$ the function $\psi(\varepsilon) = \Phi(N(u + \varepsilon h), g)$ belongs to class $C^1[0, 1]$. For N to be potential on the convex set $D(N)$ relative to Φ it is necessary and sufficient to have

$$\Phi(N'_u h, g) = \Phi(N'_u g, h) \quad \forall u \in D(N), \forall h, g \in D(N'_u). \quad (2)$$

Under this condition the potential F_N is given by

$$F_N[u] = \int_0^1 \Phi(N(u_0 + \lambda(u - u_0)), u - u_0) d\lambda + F_N[u_0], \quad (3)$$

where u_0 is a fixed element of $D(N)$.

Let us remark that N'_u is the Gâteaux derivative of N at the point u . The domain $D(N'_u)$ consists of elements $h \in U$ such that $(u + \varepsilon h) \in D(N)$ for all ε sufficiently small.

1. CONDITIONS OF POTENTIALITY AND A VARIATIONAL PRINCIPLE

Consider an ordinary differential equation

$$N(u) \equiv \sum_{i=1}^6 a_i(t)u^{(i)}(t) + a_0(t, u(t)) = 0, \quad t \in (t_0, t_1). \quad (4)$$

Here $u = u(t)$ is an unknown function, $a_i \in C^i[t_0, t_1]$ ($i = \overline{1, 6}$), $a_0 \in C^1([t_0, t_1] \times \mathbb{R})$ are given functions.

We define the domain of operator N (4) by

$$D(N) = \{u \in U = C^6[t_0, t_1] : u(t_0) = \phi_1, u(t_1) = \phi_2, u'(t_0) = \phi_3, u'(t_1) = \phi_4, \\ u''(t_0) = \phi_5, u''(t_1) = \phi_6\}, \quad (5)$$

where ϕ_i ($i = \overline{1, 6}$) are given constants.

Note that $V = C[t_0, t_1]$ and

$$D(N'_u) = \{h \in U = C^6[t_0, t_1] : h(t_0) = 0, h(t_1) = 0, h'(t_0) = 0, h'(t_1) = 0, \\ h''(t_0) = 0, h''(t_1) = 0\}.$$

Let us introduce a bilinear form

$$\Phi(v, g) = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} v(t)g(t)dt. \quad (6)$$

Theorem 2. [24] *For operator N (4) to be potential on $D(N)$ (5) relative to bilinear form (6), it is necessary and sufficient that $\forall t \in [t_0, t_1]$ the following conditions hold:*

$$a_5(t) - 3a'_6(t) = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$a_3(t) + 5a'''_6(t) - 2a'_4(t) = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$a_1(t) - 3a^{(5)}_6(t) + a'''_4(t) - a'_2(t) = 0. \quad (9)$$

Theorem 3. [24] *If conditions (7)–(9) are fulfilled then the Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action is given by*

$$F_N[u] \equiv F_N^{t_1}[u] = \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(-3a^{(4)}_6(t) + a''_4(t) - a_2(t) \right) (u'(t))^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(-3a''_6(t) + a_4(t) \right) (u''(t))^2 - \right. \\ \left. - \frac{1}{2} a_6(t) (u'''(t))^2 + B(t, u(t)) \right] dt, \quad (10)$$

where

$$B(t, u(t)) = \int_0^1 a_0(t, \tilde{u}(t, \lambda))(u(t) - u_0(t))d\lambda + B(t, u_0(t)), \quad (11)$$

$\tilde{u}(t, \lambda) = u_0(t) + \lambda(u(t) - u_0(t))$, $u_0 = u_0(t)$ is a fixed element of $D(N)$, $B \in C^2([t_0, t_1] \times \mathbb{R})$.

Theorem 4. [24] *Conditions (7)–(9) are fulfilled if and only if equation (4) takes the form*

$$N(u) \equiv a_6(t)u^{(6)}(t) + 3a_6'(t)u^{(5)}(t) + a_4(t)u^{(4)}(t) + \left(2a_4'(t) - 5a_6'''(t)\right)u'''(t) + a_2(t)u''(t) + \left(3a_6^{(5)}(t) - a_4'''(t) + a_2'(t)\right)u'(t) + B_u'(t, u(t)) = 0. \quad (12)$$

2. ON SYMMETRIES OF THE HAMILTON-OSTROGRADSKII ACTION

Assume that the functional (10) is defined on the set $C^3[t_0, t_1]$. Consider an infinitesimal transformation

$$\bar{u}(t, \varepsilon) = u(t) + \varepsilon S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \quad (13)$$

on $D(N)$ (5).

The function $S \in C^3([t_0, t_1] \times \mathbb{R}^4)$ is called a generator of transformation (13).

Definition 2. Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action (10) is called an absolute invariant with respect to transformation (13), if

$$F_N^{T_1}[\bar{u}] = F_N^{T_1}[u] + o(\varepsilon) \quad \forall u \in D(N), \quad \forall T_1 : t_0 \leq T_1 \leq t_1.$$

Definition 3. Transformation (13) is called a divergence symmetry of Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action (10), if there exists a function $f \in C^1([t_0, t_1] \times \mathbb{R}^6)$ such that

$$F_N^{T_1}[\bar{u}] = F_N^{T_1}[u] + \varepsilon \int_{t_0}^{T_1} \frac{d}{dt} f(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t), u^{(4)}(t), u^{(5)}(t)) dt + o(\varepsilon) \quad \forall u \in D(N), \quad \forall T_1 : t_0 \leq T_1 \leq t_1. \quad (14)$$

Note that the function S is also called a generator of the symmetry (absolute or divergence), and symmetries of the Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action are also called variational symmetries.

Theorem 5. *Transformation (13) is a divergence symmetry of Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action (10) if and only if*

$$N(u)S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) + \frac{d}{dt} \left[-a_6(t)u'''(t) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) + \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u''(t) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) = \\
& = \frac{d}{dt} \left((-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u''(t) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) - \\
& - \left((-3a_6'''(t) + a_4'(t))u''(t) + (-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u'''(t) \right) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) = \\
& = \frac{d}{dt} \left((-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u''(t) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) - \\
& - \frac{d}{dt} \left[\left((-3a_6'''(t) + a_4'(t))u''(t) + (-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u'''(t) \right) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right] + \\
& + \left((-3a_6^{(4)}(t) + a_4''(t))u''(t) + 2(-3a_6'''(t) + a_4'(t))u'''(t) + \right. \\
& \left. + (-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u^{(4)}(t) \right) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)), \quad (18)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -a_6(t)u'''(t) \frac{d^3}{dt^3} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) = \\
& = \frac{d}{dt} \left(-a_6(t)u'''(t) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& + (a_6'(t)u'''(t) + a_6(t)u^{(4)}(t)) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) = \\
& = \frac{d}{dt} \left(-a_6(t)u'''(t) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& + \frac{d}{dt} \left((a_6'(t)u'''(t) + a_6(t)u^{(4)}(t)) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) - \\
& - (a_6''(t)u'''(t) + 2a_6'(t)u^{(4)}(t) + a_6(t)u^{(5)}(t)) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) = \\
& = \frac{d}{dt} \left(-a_6(t)u'''(t) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& + \frac{d}{dt} \left((a_6'(t)u'''(t) + a_6(t)u^{(4)}(t)) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) - \\
& - \frac{d}{dt} \left((a_6''(t)u'''(t) + 2a_6'(t)u^{(4)}(t) + a_6(t)u^{(5)}(t)) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& + (a_6'''(t)u'''(t) + 3a_6''(t)u^{(4)}(t) + 3a_6'(t)u^{(5)}(t) + a_6(t)u^{(6)}(t)) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)). \quad (19)
\end{aligned}$$

Further,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{d}{dt} \left(-a_6(t)u'''(t) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& \quad + \frac{d}{dt} \left((a_6'(t)u'''(t) + a_6(t)u^{(4)}(t)) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& \quad + \frac{d}{dt} \left((-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u''(t) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) - \\
& - \frac{d}{dt} \left[\left((-3a_6'''(t) + a_4'(t))u''(t) + (-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u'''(t) \right) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right] - \\
& \quad - \frac{d}{dt} \left((a_6''(t)u'''(t) + 2a_6'(t)u^{(4)}(t) + a_6(t)u^{(5)}(t)) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& \quad + \frac{d}{dt} \left((-3a_6^{(4)}(t) + a_4''(t) - a_2(t))u'(t) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& + \left(\left(3a_6^{(5)}(t) - a_4'''(t) + a_2'(t) \right)u'(t) + a_2(t)u''(t) + \left(2a_4'(t) - 5a_6'''(t) \right)u'''(t) + a_4(t)u^{(4)}(t) + \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 3a_6'(t)u^{(5)}(t) + a_6(t)u^{(6)}(t) \right) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) + \\
& \quad + \frac{\partial B(t, u(t))}{\partial u} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) - \\
& \quad - \frac{d}{dt} f(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t), u^{(4)}(t), u^{(5)}(t)) = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, taking into consideration (12), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{d}{dt} \left(-a_6(t)u'''(t) \frac{d^2}{dt^2} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right) + \\
& + \frac{d}{dt} \left[\left((-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u''(t) + a_6'(t)u'''(t) + a_6(t)u^{(4)}(t) \right) \frac{d}{dt} S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right] + \\
& + \frac{d}{dt} \left[\left((-3a_6^{(4)}(t) + a_4''(t) - a_2(t))u'(t) + (3a_6'''(t) - a_4'(t))u''(t) + (2a_6''(t) - a_4(t))u'''(t) - \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. - 2a_6'(t)u^{(4)}(t) - a_6(t)u^{(5)}(t) \right) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) \right] + \\
& \quad + N(u)S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) - \\
& \quad - \frac{d}{dt} f(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t), u^{(4)}(t), u^{(5)}(t)) = 0,
\end{aligned}$$

i. e. we obtain condition (15). Obviously, condition (15) is also sufficient. \square

Consequence 1. If transformation (13) is a divergence symmetry of Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action (10), then

$$\begin{aligned}
 I(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t), u^{(4)}(t), u^{(5)}(t)) = & \\
 = -a_6(t)u'''(t)\frac{d^2}{dt^2}S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) + & \\
 + \left((-3a_6''(t) + a_4(t))u''(t) + a_6'(t)u'''(t) + a_6(t)u^{(4)}(t) \right) \frac{d}{dt}S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) + & \\
 + \left((-3a_6^{(4)}(t) + a_4''(t) - a_2(t))u'(t) + (3a_6'''(t) - a_4'(t))u''(t) + (2a_6''(t) - a_4(t))u'''(t) - \right. & \\
 \left. - 2a_6'(t)u^{(4)}(t) - a_6(t)u^{(5)}(t) \right) S(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t)) - & \\
 - f(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t), u^{(4)}(t), u^{(5)}(t)) &
 \end{aligned}$$

is a first integral of the ordinary differential equation (4).

3. ON SYMMETRIES AND FIRST INTEGRALS OF EQUATION (4) WITH POTENTIAL OPERATOR N

Suppose that $S \in C^6([t_0, t_1] \times \mathbb{R})$.

Definition 4. A transformation

$$\bar{u}(t, \varepsilon) = u(t) + \varepsilon S(t, u) \tag{20}$$

is called a symmetry of equation (4) if, for any sufficiently small ε and any solution u to this equation, the function \bar{u} (20) is also a solution to equation (4).

Note that in this case the operator S is also called a generator of the symmetry of equation (4).

The invariance criterion was obtained in [25] and formulated in the form of the following theorem.

Theorem 6. A transformation

$$\bar{u} = u + \varepsilon \tilde{S}(u)$$

is a symmetry of equation $N(u) = 0$ if and only if

$$N'_u \tilde{S}(u) = 0 \tag{21}$$

on solutions to this equation.

Theorem 7. *If operator N (4) is potential on $D(N)$ (5) with respect to bilinear form (6), S_1, S_2 are generators of symmetries of equation (4), then*

$$\begin{aligned}
 J[t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), u'''(t), u^{(4)}(t), u^{(5)}(t)] &= [-a_2(t) + a_4''(t) - 3a_6^{(4)}(t)] S_1(t, u) D_t S_2(t, u) + \\
 &+ [a_2(t) - a_4''(t) + 3a_6^{(4)}(t)] D_t S_1(t, u) S_2(t, u) + \\
 &+ [-a_4'(t) + 3a_6'''(t)] S_1(t, u) D_t^2 S_2(t, u) + \\
 &+ [a_4'(t) - 3a_6'''(t)] D_t^2 S_1(t, u) S_2(t, u) + [-a_4(t) + 2a_6''(t)] S_1(t, u) D_t^3 S_2(t, u) + \\
 &+ [a_4(t) - 3a_6''(t)] D_t S_1(t, u) D_t^2 S_2(t, u) + [-a_4(t) + 3a_6''(t)] D_t^2 S_1(t, u) D_t S_2(t, u) + \\
 &+ [a_4(t) - 2a_6''(t)] D_t^3 S_1(t, u) S_2(t, u) - 2a_6'(t) S_1(t, u) D_t^4 S_2(t, u) + a_6'(t) D_t S_1(t, u) D_t^3 S_2(t, u) - \\
 &- a_6'(t) D_t^3 S_1(t, u) D_t S_2(t, u) + 2a_6'(t) D_t^4 S_1(t, u) S_2(t, u) - a_6(t) S_1(t, u) D_t^5 S_2(t, u) + \\
 &+ a_6(t) D_t S_1(t, u) D_t^4 S_2(t, u) - a_6(t) D_t^2 S_1(t, u) D_t^3 S_2(t, u) + a_6(t) D_t^3 S_1(t, u) D_t^2 S_2(t, u) - \\
 &- a_6(t) D_t^4 S_1(t, u) D_t S_2(t, u) + a_6(t) D_t^5 S_1(t, u) S_2(t, u) \quad (22)
 \end{aligned}$$

is a first integral of this equation.

Proof. Let us find the Gâteaux derivative of the operator N . We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 N'_u h &= a_6(t) h^{(6)}(t) + a_5(t) h^{(5)}(t) + a_4(t) h^{(4)}(t) + a_3(t) h'''(t) + \\
 &+ a_2(t) h''(t) + a_1(t) h'(t) + (a_0)'_u(t, u(t)) h(t).
 \end{aligned}$$

Further,

$$g N'_u h = \left(\sum_{i=1}^6 a_i(t) h^{(i)}(t) + (a_0)'_u(t, u(t)) h(t) \right) g(t).$$

We obtain

$$J_1 = a_1(t) h'(t) g(t) = D_t(a_1(t) h(t) g(t)) - (a_1(t) g'(t) + a_1'(t) g(t)) h(t),$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_2 = a_2(t) h''(t) g(t) &= D_t(a_2(t) h'(t) g(t) - a_2(t) g'(t) h(t) - a_2'(t) g(t) h(t)) + \\
 &+ a_2(t) g''(t) h(t) + 2a_2'(t) g'(t) h(t) + a_2''(t) g(t) h(t),
 \end{aligned}$$

$$J_3 = a_3(t) h'''(t) g(t) = D_t(a_3(t) h''(t) g(t) - a_3(t) g'(t) h'(t) - a_3'(t) g(t) h'(t)) +$$

$$+D_t(a_3(t)g''(t)h(t) + a_3''(t)g(t)h(t) + 2a_3'(t)g'(t)h(t)) - a_3(t)g'''(t)h(t) - \\ -3a_3''(t)g'(t)h(t) - 3a_3'(t)g''(t)h(t) - a_3'''(t)g(t)h(t),$$

$$J_4 = a_4(t)h^{(4)}(t)g(t) = D_t(a_4(t)h'''(t)g(t) - a_4(t)g'(t)h''(t)) + \\ +D_t(a_4(t)g''(t)h'(t) - a_4(t)g'''(t)h(t) + 2a_4'(t)g'(t)h'(t)) + \\ +D_t(a_4''(t)g(t)h'(t) - 3a_4''(t)g'(t)h(t) - a_4'''(t)g(t)h(t) - 3a_4'(t)g''(t)h(t)) - \\ -D_t(a_4'(t)g(t)h''(t)) + a_4(t)g^{(4)}(t)h(t) + 4a_4'''(t)g'(t)h(t) + 6a_4''(t)g''(t)h(t) - \\ +4a_4'(t)g'''(t)h(t) + a_4^{(4)}(t)g(t)h(t),$$

$$J_5 = a_5(t)h^{(5)}(t)g(t) = D_t(a_5(t)h^{(4)}(t)g(t)) - D_t(a_5(t)g'(t)h'''(t)) + \\ +D_t(a_5(t)g''(t)h''(t)) - D_t(a_5(t)g'''(t)h'(t)) + \\ +D_t(a_5(t)g^{(4)}(t)h(t)) - 5a_5'(t)g^{(4)}(t)h(t) - a_5(t)g^{(5)}(t)h(t) + \\ +2D_t(a_5'(t)g'(t)h''(t)) - 3D_t(a_5''(t)g'(t)h'(t)) + 4D_t(a_5'''(t)g'(t)h(t)) - \\ -5a_5^{(4)}(t)g'(t)h(t) - 10a_5'''(t)g''(t)h(t) + 6D_t(a_5''(t)g''(t)h(t)) - \\ -10a_5''(t)g'''(t)h(t) - 3D_t(a_5'(t)g''(t)h'(t)) + 4D_t(a_5'(t)g'''(t)h(t)) - \\ -D_t(a_5'(t)g(t)h'''(t)) + D_t(a_5''(t)g(t)h''(t)) - D_t(a_5'''(t)g(t)h'(t)) + \\ +D_t(a_5^{(4)}(t)g(t)h(t)) - a_5^{(5)}(t)g(t)h(t),$$

$$J_6 = a_6(t)h^{(6)}(t)g(t)dt = \\ = D_t(a_6(t)h^{(5)}(t)g(t)) - D_t(a_6(t)g'(t)h^{(4)}(t)) + D_t(a_6(t)g''(t)h'''(t)) - \\ -D_t(a_6(t)g'''(t)h''(t)) + D_t(a_6(t)g^{(4)}(t)h'(t)) - 5D_t(a_6'(t)g^{(4)}(t)h(t)) + \\ +15a_6''(t)g^{(4)}(t)h(t) + 6a_6'(t)g^{(5)}(t)h(t) - D_t(a_6(t)g^{(5)}(t)h(t)) + \\ +a_6(t)g^{(6)}(t)h(t) + 2D_t(a_6'(t)g'(t)h'''(t)) - 3D_t(a_6''(t)g'(t)h''(t)) + \\ +4D_t(a_6'''(t)g'(t)h'(t)) - 5D_t(a_6^{(4)}(t)g'(t)h(t)) + 6a_6^{(5)}(t)g'(t)h(t) + \\ +15a_6^{(4)}(t)g''(t)h(t) - 10D_t(a_6'''(t)g''(t)h(t)) + 20a_6'''(t)g'''(t)h(t) +$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +6D_t(a_6''(t)g''(t)h'(t)) - 10D_t(a_6''(t)g'''(t)h(t)) - 3D_t(a_6'(t)g''(t)h''(t)) + \\
& +4D_t(a_6'(t)g'''(t)h'(t)) - D_t(a_6'(t)g(t)h^{(4)}(t)) + D_t(a_6''(t)g(t)h'''(t)) - \\
& -D_t(a_6'''(t)g(t)h''(t)) + D_t(a_6^{(4)}(t)g(t)h'(t)) - D_t(a_6^{(5)}(t)g(t)h(t)) + a_6^{(6)}(t)g(t)h(t).
\end{aligned}$$

Then taking into consideration conditions (7)–(9) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
gN'_u h = hN'_u g + D_t \left\{ \right. & [-a_2(t) + a_4''(t) - 3a_6^{(4)}(t)]h(t)g'(t) + [a_2(t) - a_4''(t) + 3a_6^{(4)}(t)]h'(t)g(t) + \\
& + [-a_4'(t) + 3a_6'''(t)]h(t)g''(t) + [a_4'(t) - 3a_6'''(t)]h''(t)g(t) + [-a_4(t) + 2a_6''(t)]h(t)g'''(t) + \\
& + [a_4(t) - 3a_6''(t)]h'(t)g''(t) + [-a_4(t) + 3a_6''(t)]h''(t)g'(t) + \\
& + [a_4(t) - 2a_6''(t)]h'''(t)g(t) - 2a_6'(t)h(t)g^{(4)}(t) + a_6'(t)h'(t)g'''(t) - \\
& - a_6'(t)h'''(t)g'(t) + 2a_6'(t)h^{(4)}(t)g(t) - a_6(t)h(t)g^{(5)}(t) + \\
& + a_6(t)h'(t)g^{(4)}(t) - a_6(t)h''(t)g'''(t) + a_6(t)h'''(t)g''(t) - \\
& \left. - a_6(t)h^{(4)}(t)g'(t) + a_6(t)h^{(5)}(t)g(t) \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting $S_1(t, u)$ and $S_2(t, u)$ into the last expression instead of h and g , respectively, and taking into account (21), we conclude that J of the form (22) is the first integral of the considered equation. □

CONCLUSION

In the paper, we use some methods based on application of transformation of variables to establish invariance of the given sixth-order ordinary differential equation with the potential operator and the corresponding Hamilton-Ostrogradskii action. Some first integrals of the considered equation are also found.

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